

Christianity in Antioch. From the Apostolic Era to the Islamic conquest

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Antioch has been one of the great centers of Christianity since the times of the New Testament. The origins of Christianity in the city dates from the time of the Apostles. Antioch is mentioned in the Book of Acts (11:26), as the city that the followers of Christ were first ironically referred to as "Christians". In the Book of Acts, which offers an account of the first years of the Church, Antioch is the second most frequently mentioned city. One of the original seven deacons, Nicholas, was a convert from Antioch and perhaps the first Christian from that city (Acts 6:5). During the persecution which led to the death of St Stephen the First Martyr, members of the fledgling Christian community in Jerusalem fled to Antioch for refuge. According to the tradition of the Church, the See of Antioch was founded by St Peter in 34 CE (mentioned in the Book of Acts, 2:26). Peter was either followed or joined by the Apostles Paul and Barnabas, who preached there to both gentiles and Jews, who seem to have been numerous in the city. It was in Antioch that one of the first conflicts within the newly-founded Church developed between Peter and Paul, regarding the necessity of circumcision for male gentile converts to Christianity. The resolution of this conflict, at the Apostolic Council of Jerusalem in 48-50 CE, determined the direction of the Antiochian mission to the gentiles. It was from Antioch, after all, that Paul and Barnabas departed for their first and their second missionary journeys, in 48 CE from Antioch to Cyprus, Antioch of Pisidia, Iconium, Lystra, Derbe; and in 51 CE from Antioch to Cilicia, Lycaonia, Galatia, Troas, Philippi, Thessalonica, Berea, Athens, and Corinth. After spending almost seven years in Antioch, St Peter left for Rome. He was succeeded by Euodius, one of the 72 disciples of Christ, who is thus counted in early episcopal lists as the first successor to the Antiochian Throne of Peter. The See of Antioch produced several important personalities, such as St Ignatius of Antioch, the second successor to Peter, a victorious martyr during the reign of Emperor Trajan and an invaluable historical source for the structure of Church life. His Epistles, written en route to his martyrdom in Rome, bear abundant testimony to the nature of the early hierarchical structure of the Church and to general Church order. In addition to Ignatius, mention must be made of the works of Theophilus (169-182 CE), the sixth successor to Peter, who defended Christian doctrine in his writings against heretics and pagans. At the beginning of the fifth century the Patriarchate of Antioch held ecclesiastical hegemony over a large area including Cyprus, Syria, Palestine, Arabia and Mesopotamia. Though still under some Antiochian influence, the Churches of Georgia and Persia were granted ecclesiastical independence by their Mother Church of Antioch. Antioch could not, however, long hold on to this prestigious position and would lose much to the doctrinal conflicts which either originated there or had as their authors men from the Patriarchate of Antioch. In the fifth century the Patriarch of Constantinople, Nestorius, originated from Antioch, was condemned at the Council of Ephesus (431) for his heretical teachings. Despite this condemnation, many Christians in Persia and the East refused to accept it and broke from Orthodoxy by establishing the Nestorian or Assyrian Church. Furthermore, and during the same century, the Monophysite heresy, whose leading opponent was Saint Cyril of Alexandria, gained a foothold in Syria from where many of its leading and most respected proponents came. The monophysite heresy was condemned at the Council of Chalcedon in 451. However, as in the case of Nestorianism, many Christians including a number of Antiochians refused to accept this condemnation. The subsequent establishment of a Monophysite hierarchy (Jacobite) in the sixth century weakened the See of Antioch. At this same time the geographical extent of the Patriarchate was reduced by decisions of the Ecumenical Councils. In 431 the Church of Cyprus was granted independence from Antioch, and in 451 the Patriarchate of Jerusalem was established and given jurisdiction of Palestine and Arabia. In the early seventh century the Byzantine Empire was threatened by the Persians in the East. In an attempt to reconcile the Orthodox and the Jacobite Monophysites to provide a united front against the invaders, Byzantine Emperor Heraclius proposed the compromise doctrine of Monothelism. However the Orthodox would accept no political compromise when it came to matters of the Faith and at the Council of Constantinople in 680 Monothelism was rejected as heresy. Very quickly thereafter Monothelism died out, except at the Antiochian monastery of Beit-Maroon on the Orontes River (the supporters of this heresy became known as Maronites). These three schisms along with the geographical reduction of the Patriarchate of Antioch reduced the See from its former prestige. The city of Antioch and the Patriarchate continued its decline as the administrative center of Eastern Christianity when it suffered a series of earthquakes, attacks and occupations by hostile cultural and religious elements. The city was captured and ravaged by the Persians in 538-540 and again in 611. After the Byzantine recovery of the area and the defeat of the Persians under Emperor Heraclius, Islam arose as a long range religiously motivated threat to the Christian Byzantine Empire. Antioch was one of the first victories of the advancing wave of Islam, falling in 638.

Date Range: 34 CE - 638 CE

Region: Antioch (Antakya) in modern-day Syria

Region tags: Eastern Mediterranean, Byzantium, Antioch

Antioch, the "Queen City" for, as the capital of the Roman Diocese of the East went far in extending her ecclesiastical jurisdiction and influence throughout the Middle and Far East.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: D. S. Wallace-Hadrill: *Christian Antioch: A Study of Early Christian Thought in the East*, Cambridge University Press 2009
- Source 2: Magnus Zetterholm: *The Formation of Christianity in Antioch. A Social-Scientific Approach to the Separation Between Judaism and Christianity*, Taylor & Francis 2003
- Source 3: Raymond Edward Brown, John P. Meier: *Antioch and Rome. New Testament Cradles of Catholic Christianity*, Paulist Press 1983
- Source 1: Isabella Sandwell, Janet Huskinson: *Culture and Society in Later Roman Antioch*, Oxbow Books 2017

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://www.wikiwand.com/en/School_of_Antioch
- Source 1 Description: Catechetical School of Antioch
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.worldhistory.org/Antiochia/>
- Source 2 Description: Antioch
- Source 3 URL: http://vrc.princeton.edu/archives/search?query=Mosaic+of+Megalopsychia&query_type=keyword&record_types%5B%5D=Item&record_types%5B%5D=File&record_types%5B%5D=Coll
- Source 3 Description: Photographs of the Mosaic of Megalopsychia in Antioch.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YJO4e34NDkQ>
- Source 1 Description: The megalopsychia mosaic (video)
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.antiochpatriarchate.org/en/home/>
- Source 2 Description: Greek Orthodox Patriarchate of Antioch and All the East

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: In the early Christian centuries in Antioch, pagan, Jewish and some gnostic sects exercised great influence upon all religious activity in Syria. Hence, the primitive Antiochene Church was formed by converts from these three great religious groups. The relationship and interaction between these groups was not always easy and, during the Byzantine era, there were many cases of tension and conflict. Furthermore, it should be noted the Maronite Church, founded ca. in the 5th century. The Maronite Church follows the Antiochene Tradition. Any Catholic may attend any Eastern Catholic liturgy and fulfill his or her canonical obligations at an Eastern Catholic parish. Any Catholic may attend any Eastern Catholic parish or service and receive any sacrament from an Eastern Catholic priest since all belong to the Catholic Church. Maronites who do not reside within a convenient distance to a local Maronite Church are permitted to attend other Catholic churches while retaining their Maronite membership.

Reference: Maxwell, Jaclyn . *Christianization and Communication in Late Antiquity: John Chrysostom and His Congregation in Antioch*. Cambridge : Cambridge University Press, 2006.

Reference: Zetterholm, Magnus. *The Formation of Christianity in Antioch: A Social-scientific Approach to the Separation Between Judaism and Christianity*. London: Routledge, 2003.

Reference: Sandwell, Isabella . *Religious Identity in Late Antiquity: Greeks, Jews and Christians in Antioch. Greek Culture in the Roman World*. Cambridge : Cambridge University Press, 2007.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Antioch itself did not suffer as severely as did the neighboring country districts from religious conflicts. According to Libanius only four of the great temples of the city remained twenty years after Julian. In the early years of the fifth century Rabbula journeyed in a heat of zeal to destroy pagan shrines and suffered for it at the hands of their priests for although destruction of temples had been permitted by law since 399, the temple hierarchies were in no mood to take it lying down.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

Notes: A fine example of apostasy is Severus, the Patriarch of Antioch, who has adopted non-Chalcedonianism. Severus refused to affirm the Council of Chalcedon, therefore the emperor ordered to arrest Severus and cut out his tongue. On 25 September 518 Severus fled Antioch by boat to Alexandria, where he was well received by the city's inhabitants. Severus' arrival in Egypt is celebrated by the Coptic Orthodox Church on 12 October.

Reference: Allen, Pauline, and C. T. Hayward. Severus of Antioch. London, New York: Routledge, 2004.

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– Yes

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 100

Notes: According to Libanius, there were approx. 150,000 inhabitants in the city, a word which would ordinarily mean all human beings of any age, sex, or social status, John Chrysostom also mentions in one of his homilies (delivered between 386 and 393), that in his own time there were 100,000 Christians in Antioch. This number may refer to orthodox Christians only who belonged to the Great Church.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 75

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (with smaller religious groups not officially allowed but in practice tolerated)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:
 - Yes
 - ↳ A single leader of a local community:
 - No
 - ↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:
 - No
 - ↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):
 - Yes
 - ↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:
 - Number of levels [numeric value]: 4
 - No
- ↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are leaders considered fallible:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:
 - No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:
– Yes

↳ Are they oral:
– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:
– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:
– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:
– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:
– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:
– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:
– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:
– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:
– Yes

↳ Temples:
– Yes

↳ Altars:
– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Devotional markers:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:
 - Yes [specify]: Walls, cave Church of St. Peter
 - Notes: The walls of the city encompassed almost 450 hectares (1,100 acres). St. Peter's Cave Church is in fact a cave carved into the mountainside on Mount Starius with a depth of 42 ft, a width of 31 ft. and a height of 23 ft.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: Antioch is known for its great mosaics, the so-called "Antioch mosaics". The mosaics combine artistic styles of ancient Greece and Rome, and the art of early Christianity. The mosaics are incredibly large, with "The Worcester Hunt" measuring 20.5 feet x 23.3 feet. The mosaics range in design from realistic imagery and scenes, to purely geometric patterns. The mosaics include both white and colored marble as well as white and colored limestone.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- Only religious public space
- Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: The Domus Aurea or the Great Church in Antioch was the cathedral where the Patriarch of Antioch preached. It was one of the churches whose construction was started during the reign of Constantine the Great. The church became a major point of the controversy between Christians and Julian the Apostate when the latter closed the cathedral in response to the burning of an ancient temple to Apollo in the nearby suburb of Daphne. From 526 to 587 it suffered from a series of earthquakes, fires and Persian attacks, before being finally destroyed in another earthquake in 588, after which it was not rebuilt.

Reference: Downey, Glanville. "The Pagan Virtue of Megalopsychia in Byzantine Syria" 76 (1945). <https://doi.org/doi:10.2307/283341>.

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: The Domus Aurea, or the Great Church, was built on the island between the two main branches of the Orontes River, where the Imperial Palace was located.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: Nevertheless, in modern times the cave Church of St. Peter is considered as a pilgrimage site, since it is believed that there St. Peter first celebrated Mass. Furthermore, south of the cave Church of St. Peter is situated the Iron Gate, which was one of the actual entrances of biblical Antioch.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: Spirit and body, according to the Christian tradition and belief, are created simultaneously.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Notes: The Christian belief in afterlife (or more generic, in life after death) does not involve a spatial location where the dead would reside. On the contrary, life after death is depicted mostly as a state of being (of different sort), a different situation, rather than a being in a different place

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Reference: Bear, Carl. Christian Funeral Practices in Late Fourth-century Antioch (phd Diss.). Berkeley, Los Angeles: Graduate Theological Union, 2017.
<https://www.proquest.com/openview/b0333b830326f3eb8153b7f13f599501/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750>.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– Yes [specify]: omnipotence

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– No

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - No
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - No
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - Yes [specify]: prayer, miracles
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - No
 - ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - No
- Yes
 - ↳ A supreme high god is present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: omnipotence

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

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– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

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– Yes

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– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– No

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 - ↳ In dreams:
 - No
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - No
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - Yes [specify]: prayer
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - No

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

- Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

- No

↳ Courage (generic):

- Field doesn't know

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

- Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

- Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

- Yes

- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - No
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - No
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes

- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 4

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Reference: Risse, Cuentor. "Christian Welfare: Rise of the Xenodocheion". University of California, 2008. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/DOI:10.13140/RG.2.1.2717.9128..>

Reference: Poe, Mary Anne. "Good News for the Poor: Christian Influences on Social Welfare". Palos Heights, IL: North American Association of Christians in Social Work, 2016.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: The Antiochian School (founded ca 200 CE) represented an historical and concrete exegesis of the Scripture and understanding of Christ. The Alexandrian School, on the other hand, represented a more symbolical and allegorical interpretation. Ultimately it was the balance that was struck between these two tendencies in early Christian thought which produced the refined expression which we today designate as Christian doctrine, the fundamental tenets of the Faith, i.e., the nature of Christ, the nature of the Holy Trinity, the nature of Man. It was the famous School of Antioch which provided the necessary practical, concrete, and human balance to the more mystical approach of the Alexandrians.

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– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: Albeit he lived during the twelfth century, one has to mention Theodore Balsamon, Patriarch of Antioch from 1193 to 1195, who wrote the "Scholia", a commentary on the Nomocanon of Photios, the standard work on Eastern Orthodox ecclesiastical and imperial laws and decrees. The work was commissioned by the Emperor Manuel I and the Patriarch Michael III. He also compiled a collection of ecclesiastical constitutions (the Syntagma) and wrote other works, many of which concern the ongoing debate between the Eastern and Western Churches following the schism of 1054.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: It should be noted that after the fall of Antioch in 638, the city was recovered, in the tenth century, by the Byzantines under the Emperor Nicephorus Phocas. The Turks captured the city in 1086, but their occupation was cut short by the invading armies from the West, the Crusades, which occupied the area in 1099. For the next 150 years the Church of Antioch was reduced to imposed Roman Catholic submission. Under the pretext of saving the Holy Land and its Christian inhabitants from the Turks, the Latin Crusaders replaced by force the Orthodox patriarch and hierarchy with those subject to the Roman Church. In 1154 Antioch was retaken from its Western occupiers by the Byzantine Emperor Emmanuel Comnenus who, allowing Latin occupation to continue under his overlordship, insisted that an Orthodox patriarch be returned to the city. This agreement to have the Antiochian Patriarch appointed from Constantinople did not last long and many subsequent Orthodox patriarchs of Antioch, such as the famous twelfth century canonist Theodore IV, Balsamon, were unable to live under the hostile Latin occupation and remained either in Constantinople or elsewhere. Between the thirteenth and eighteenth centuries the patriarchs of Antioch were again elected and consecrated by the Antiochian Synod of local Syrian hierarchs. When the Mameluk Sultans of Egypt came to power (ca 1260-1269), the Orthodox hierarchs were reinstated to the See of Antioch, but they were refused permission to return to the city itself, and the center of the administration was permanently transferred in the sixteenth century to Damascus. Thus the Patriarchate of Antioch became more and more specifically identified with the Christian Arab population, while maintaining its Byzantine Orthodox traditions and rites.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

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